

“ WHAT WE LEARN WITH PLEASURE, WE NEVER FORGET”

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051495>

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Annotation: *This article presents the concept of helpful methods in learning foreign languages with pleasure, a strange language which is learnt by strong love and desire, will stay in mind forever. It is claimed that this process is important not only during the lesson but also creating English speaking atmosphere in our everyday life.*

Key words: *challenging system, tricks and approaches, increase focus, conversation questions, favorite activities, unforgettable, appropriate range, best motivation*

Learning foreign language is the demand of the life period. Improving your vocabulary is one of the best things you can do to keep moving forward in a language but do you ever have a rough time remembering hard vocabulary words in English. Everyone knows that it doesn't work without reciting a new staff of words which are necessary for speech.

It is possibly easy if your memory is good enough. You may read and learn by heart with pleasure. But some people often complain about their memory even if they try to do their best, the technique works very slow or easily forgettable. After having practiced heavily I've realized some methods which can be definitely useful in increasing your vocabulary level.

“Language is the road map of a culture. It tells you where its people come from and where they are going” - Rita Mae Brown

Love has always been the vital point of the life. The relationship of different spheres with love makes it effective in obtaining the goals. As the education is challenging system, the benefit of using love in teaching may be productive.

At this point, one needs to think about how to engage the students in creation the interest for English language in the classroom.

Here, let's move the stages of activities which are helpful among the students. Without having any interest to language they are bored and make teachers get frustrated when they are trying doing their best, providing enjoyment and basement.

By supporting a little afford with tricks and approaches the classes can be liven up. Minor changes or improvement are helpful in recognizing the foreign language positively.

The following steps are suggested to involve the students engaged in the classroom:

1. To explain the importance of English in students' life
2. To identify pupils' knowledge and plan the lesson by their necessities.
3. Taking notes through little comments or class quizzes. .
4. The appropriate activities to create pleasant environment to pupils.
5. Keep your "audiences" in mind.

1. To explain the importance of English in students' life

"Learning another language is not only learning different words for the same things, but learning another way to think about things." -Flora Lewis

Young learners in the classroom may be different aged: teenagers, adolescents or adults. They are sent reasonably by their parents or someone who is responsible for their knowledge. Some of them will already have the desire to study and try to achieve their goals. There is not any reason of participating in tutoring classes or no necessity to explain the importance of learning English.

The problem is on unengaged pupils and undirected desire. The suggestion of teacher may increase their focus, engagement and the reason of involvement. There are many ways of proving that and show how English skills are beneficial to them.

Some pupils have difficulties in identifying their future profession, they rely on their parents or to any of their ideals who achieved in life. Language possibilities may show their abilities in conversation questions and interviews. Here, class level must be considered.

Small talks, debates are also essential in creating English speaking atmosphere in the classroom. Pupils study and work in various kind of situations as travelling abroad, asking for details or searching for directions.

They should be explained even if they don't live in abroad or without any plan to future, they may relax by listening lyrics, songs in English. Isn't it very enjoyable to understand the meaning of bands while listening your favorite singer or pop star.

The most important point is to demonstrate pupils the relevance of English with life. And our duty is help them to see the world widely and learn little more.

2. To identify pupils' knowledge and plan the lesson by their necessities.

“He who speaks a bit of a foreign language has more delight in it than he who speaks it well; pleasure goes along with superficial knowledge.” Friedrich Nietzsche

Teachers' responsibility in planning lesson should be naturally. If everything is organized considering pupils' mind and needs, they will relatively be more attentive in concentrating data.

By irrelevant information successful class may be misled and lost its importance. Additionally, school libraries are the main source which can provide pupils with aimed directions. By reading the experience of writers or older people they may have chance to choose the most appropriate one for themselves.

Funny activities such as questionnaires make pupils enjoy during the lesson by sharing ideas and note down your students weekly or daily activities, interests. For example: who has a pet or a baby brother, who likes to play musical instruments, what are their favorite sweets and etc.

These kind of interesting activities help teachers to break the barrier between the pupils and to know closely each other.

3. Taking notes through little comments or class quizzes.

This activity is the continue of the concept above. These tools are helpful to shake less interested or unengaged pupils. While listening their reply you demonstrate that you take notes of what is going on their lives.

It works efficiently at any age group of pupils who are bored or totally fed up with lessons.

The most significant thing is to work on their favorite activities as the attendance of any sport club, music club, cooking habits, learning centers and etc.

Next stage is being interested in their last weekend or plans for near future.

For example:

1. What book are you reading?
2. What impressions did you take from the book you have read?
3. How did you spend your last weekend?
4. Who do you recommend me to listen?
5. What is the trend band nowadays?

The reason of demonstrating teacher's interest to pupils life will soften the situation in the classroom and involve them to reach the goals in English

learning sphere. After some period of time you may be able to see the improvement in their knowledge and in classroom activities.

4. The appropriate activities to create pleasant environment to pupils

“To learn a language is to have one more window from which to look at the world.”-Chinese Proverb.

As choosing suitable activities are required a great talent, experience from teachers as the surprises become unforgettable for students. Because when something strange happens, by adding some pleasure to classroom, teachers and activities they have done will stay in our memory forever.

So, the more funny and engaging activities are chosen the more productive and enjoyable is the lesson. These kind of activities awake a strong desire in pupils' mind.

One must be careful in planning appropriate range of learning styles. Various videos, role plays, short dialogs of everyday use or some group works support pupils feel relaxed and free.

5. Keep your “audiences” in mind.

“The more language you know, the more you are human.”- Tomas Garrigue Masaryk

The last point we recommend is making sure your lesson plan or class activities are suited to your group by considering their demands. Not every time you can play or have fun with your pupils, we must keep in mind the important tools which are necessary to teach during the year. The results of students should match to their level and be aimed to get achievements in learning language. The best motivation is when you see your pupils' results and they feel their strength limit in gaining goals.

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